

MIDAS Open v202507

Release Notes, July 2025

Overview

This document summarises the recent improvements to the MIDAS Open dataset as part of this year's annual release.

As part of this new release, an agreement was reached to include observations from stations owned by Scottish Water as well as stations without a latest owning authority listed in the MIDAS database. This specifically applies to stations that have been closed for more than 20 years and the latest authority is not retained.

The addition of these stations without a latest owning authority resulted in a considerable increase in the number of stations reporting daily rainfall observations being included in this version of the dataset. As it is not currently possible to retrace the actual latest owning authority of these stations, the authority name has been marked as "NA" in the files.

1. Inclusion of historic closed stations

Following the previous release of MIDAS Open, v202407, the coverage of daily rainfall observations in the dataset increased from about 15% to 58%. Although this was a considerable increase, this still left about 42% of daily rainfall observations in the Met Office MIDAS system missing from the open product.

A large majority of the missing observations were recorded at historic stations that had closed more than 20 years ago. As a result, the latest owning authority was not retained in the metadata and so no individual/organisation was available to grant specific approval for including these stations. Many of these stations were likely owned by one of the third-party organisations, Environment Agency, SEPA or Natural Resources Wales, whose approval for inclusion was granted last year.

A decision was made this year that observations from these historic stations could be included in this year's version of MIDAS Open, provided the stations were based in the UK and were flagged as non-commercial. These stations are now available in the v202507 version of MIDAS Open. As these stations do not have a latest owning authority available, the authority is returned as "NA" in the dataset.

2. Scottish Water stations

This year, approval was also granted from Scottish Water to include 128 stations owned by this organisation in the MIDAS Open v202507 product. Although most of these sites are now closed, they will still help to plug the coverage gap in some of the datasets, in particular daily rainfall.

3. Dataset coverage

Following the inclusion of the new stations, the MIDAS Open product now has over 90% coverage of MIDAS for all 8 datasets. Further releases of the product will attempt to bridge the coverage gap further by seeking approval from other third-party owners for inclusion of their stations' observations.

Coverage statistics for MIDAS Open v202507:

Dataset	% Total MIDAS included (v202507)	% Total MIDAS excluded (v202507)	% Met Office stations (included)	% Other stations (included)
Daily temperature	96%	4%	99%	1%
Daily rainfall	94%	6%	17%	83%
Hourly rainfall	96%	4%	95%	5%
Daily weather	96%	4%	99%	1%
Hourly weather	92%	8%	100%	0%
Soil temperature	98%	2%	100%	0%
Radiation	96%	4%	100%	0%
Mean wind	93%	7%	97%	3%